

Comparative Study of Lateritic soil in Mington Area, Hlegu Township, Yangon Region and Meyon Area, Kyaikhto Township, Mon State

Hlaing Myo Nwe *

Abstract

Lateritic soils are found in Lower Myanmar to the south of the Bago Yoma and in the Tanintharyi area, particularly near Mawlamyaing. Laterite is often confused with lateritic soils simply because the physical appearance and chemical properties are so similar. The lateritic soils are finer grained materials than laterite. An important physical difference between a laterite and a lateritic soil is that a laterite has a gravel component but a lateritic soil does not. The research areas are located in Mington area, Hlegu Township, Yangon Region and Meyon area about 9 km north of Kyaikhto Township, Mon State. The rocks are mainly composed of Tertiary mollasic sediments of Upper Pegu Group, Irrawaddy Formation of Miocene to Pliocene age and older alluvium consisting of laterite, lateritic clay and hill gravels is observed as caps of the hills in Mington area. In Meyon area, metasedimentary rocks of Mergui Group and igneous rocks are exposed. The rocks consist of slate, argillite, phyllite and quartzite whose mineral assemblages of chlorite, andalusite and quartz indicate green schist facies. The chemical result from Mington and Meyon areas are analyzed by AAS. According the chemical results, lateritic soil of Mington area contains Mn, Fe, Na, K, Ca and Mg elements. Most of the elements are lithophile elements. These elements are mainly distributed on the earth crust. Lateritic soil of the Meyon area contains Au, Ag, Cu, Pb, Zn, Mn, Fe, Na, K, Ca, Mg elements. Lithophile elements are associated with siderophile and chalcophile elements. The basic elements of the research areas are the same. Heavy minerals Au, Ag, Cu, Pb and Zn are found in Meyon area because mineralizations are found. In this research, two areas of lateritic soils are fairly different because the underlying bedrocks are different. The studied areas are used as lateritic soil for road making materials and cultivation especially cashew, rubber and oil-palm. Lateritic soil should be utilized after modification/stabilization. The most commonly used additive for soil modification or stabilization is the ordinary Portland cement and the addition of fly ash. The simplest stabilization process consists of taking soil and drying it in open-air.

Introduction

Lateritic soils are found in Lower Myanmar to the south of the Bago Yoma and in the Tanintharyi area, particularly near Mawlamyaing. Laterite is a porous, indurated, concretionary material which is usually red to reddish brown in color. The name laterite is derived from the Latin word "Later" which means "Brick earth". Lateritic soils are widely used as fill materials for various construction works in most tropical countries.

A first requirement for laterite formation is a soil horizon of appropriate thickness, containing relatively high concentrations of iron and aluminum. Materials ideally filling this requirement are produced by the weathering of igneous and metamorphic rocks in a hot, moist climate. The original soil mantle typically contains feldspathic minerals, other silicates, and minor amounts of stable minerals. Intense chemical weathering is essential for proper preparation in the soil mantle. Subsequent to the transformation of the feldspathic minerals into clay, leaching and deposition occur in which iron and aluminum oxides remain after the removal of bases and combined silica.

Laterite is found in the soil profiles of sparsely vegetated and rolling to roughly dissected terrain. Laterite is often confused with lateriti

* Lecturer, Department of Geology, Dagon University

c soils simply because the physical appearance and chemical properties are so similar. The lateritic soils are finer grained materials than laterite. An important physical difference between a laterite and a lateritic soil is that a laterite has a gravel component but a lateritic soil does not. Lateritic soils form the uppermost part of the laterite cover.

Most lateritic soils make good subgrades and can be used as a subbase material if certain precautions are taken. These soils are good for fill material and compacted fill in earth dams used for impounding water. Vegetation above a laterite or lateritic soil usually is light to sparse. Cassava, rubber, brushwoods with some scattered trees, or bamboo within forested areas are typical. When laterite is near the surface, vegetation normally is limited to low grass. Deeper laterite or lateritic soil deposits permit a denser vegetative cover. Lateritic soils are well suited for rubber tree plantations, fruit growing and horticulture. Comparative study of the two areas was made. The present research attempts to provide basic and important data for future lateritic exploration.

Location of Mingon and Meyon Areas

Mingon area is located in Mingon village in Hlegu Township, Yangon Region. It is situated about 3.2 km northeast of Central Institute of Civil Service in Paunggyi village. It lies between north latitude $17^{\circ} 20'$ to $17^{\circ} 22'$ and east longitude $96^{\circ} 12'$ to $96^{\circ} 15'$. It is included in a topographic map No.94 C/3. (Fig.1)

Figure (1) Location Map of Mingon Area

Meyon area is located about 9 km north of Kyaikhto Township in Mon State. It lies between about north latitude $17^{\circ} 24' 15''$ to $17^{\circ} 27' 30''$ and east longitude $96^{\circ} 56' 45''$ to $97^{\circ} 0' 50''$. It is included in the topographic maps No. 94 G/3 and C/15. The Meyon area can directly be reached by cars and buses because it is located on the Yangon-Mawlamyaing highway. Kyaikhto Township is accessible by train from Yangon, and then Kyaikhto to Meyon can be reached by car and motorcycle. The road from Yangon to Kyaikhto is in a usable condition for the whole year. (Fig.2)

Figure (2) Location Map of Meyon Area

Materials and Methods

Field Investigation

Representative samples of rocks and soil were collected by using GPS. In each outcrop, detailed investigations were made on rock type, inspecting the outcrop nature, grain size, weathered and fresh colour and taking the samples.

Laterite and lateritic soil samples were collected by using chanal sampling methods. First the surface is cleaned and representative chips from the lateritic soil outcrops were collected. In Mingon area, 81 soil samples were collected from the lateritic soil outcrops. Complete lateritization outcrop occurs in this area. So, soil samples were collected layer by layer. In Meyon area, 54 soil samples were collected. Soil samples localities of Mingon and Meyon areas are shown in (Figures 10 and 16).

Laboratory Methods

After conducting the field, the geological map was carried out and was checked with the aid of satellite image and aerial photos. And then, the soil sample localities were plotted in each geological map respectively.

The trace element distribution of soil samples were analyzed by using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS) at the Applied Geology Department.

Regional Geologic Setting

Geomorphologically as well as tectonically, Myanmar can be subdivided into four N-S trending major tectonic domains from west to east. They are Rakhine Coastal area, Indo-Myanmar Ranges, Inner-Myanmar Tertiary Basin, and Sino-Myanmar Ranges (Bender, 1983).

The Mingon area is located in Inner-Myanmar Tertiary Basin (Central Cenozoic Belt). The Inner-Myanmar Tertiary Basin is divided into sub-basins with Tertiary sediments and uplift areas with older sediments and crystalline rocks, with block faulting and compressional folding of the basin filling. Among these, Bago Yoma is structurally an uplifted range in the Inner-Myanmar Tertiary Basin. The study area is situated in the southern part of the Bago Yoma. The Bago Yoma is folded in an en-echelon fashion and the axis of folds is more or less parallel to the regional trend of NNE-SSW direction (Bender, 1983). The study area is mainly composed of Tertiary mollasic sediments of Upper Pegu Group and Irrawaddy Formation of Miocene to Pliocene age. Older alluvium consisting of laterite, lateritic clay and hill gravels is observed as caps of the hills.

Meyon area is situated in the Sino-Myanmar Ranges (Eastern High Land). The regional geology of Meyon area is characterized by Paleozoic metasedimentary rock and Mesozoic granitoids. The low grade metasediments are slightly folded, unfossiliferous, extensively intruded by granite and they show effects of contact metamorphism at places. The rocks are grouped under the name of Mergui Group. Mergui Group consists of slate, argillite, phyllite and minor quartzite. General structural trend is nearly N-S and NNW- SSE (Fig.3).

Granite is mainly exposed in the northern part of the area. It is poorly exposed in the study area. The alluvium is very widespread and forms a cover that conceals most of the older geology. Lateritic soils also form a cap on the igneous rocks.

■ Study Area, (1) Mingon Area, (2) Meyon Area

0 128 km

Legend

Quaternary	 Alluvium	Permian - Triassic	 Yinyaw Beds, Martaban Beds and equivalents
Miocene - Pleistocene	 Irrawaddy Group And equivalents	Paleozoic - Triassic	 Shan Dolomite Group Moulmein Limestone
Pleistocene	 Upper Pegu Group And equivalents	Paleozoic, -undifferentiated equivalent to Mogok Series	 Mergui Group Mawchi Series
Paleozoic - Mesozoic	 Undifferentiated Sediments of Eastern Burma	Mesozoic - Cenozoic age	 Metamorphics, undifferentiated
Triassic	 Bawgyo Group Kamawkala Lst.		 Granites and other Non-basic intrusives

Figure (3) Regional Geological Map of the Study Area (MGS, 2014)

Stratigraphy of Mington Area

The rocks exposed in Mington area are mainly composed of rock units of Miocene and Pliocene age, belonging to the Upper Pegu Group, Irrawaddy Formation and Alluvial sediments. Stratigraphic succession the study area is shown in Table 1.

Table (1) Stratigraphic Succession of the Mington Area

Succession	Age	Stratigraphic Symbol
Alluvium	Holocene	Q _{2al}
Laterite and lateritic clay	Pleistocene	Q _{1al}
Irrawaddy Formation	Upper Miocene-Pliocene	T-m-p _i
Obogon Formation	Mid Miocene	T-m _o
Kyaukkok Formation	Lower-Mid Miocene	T-m _k

Kyaukkok Formation

This formation is the oldest in the study area that can be found near the Aingwaing Chaung Bridge. This unit is composed of bluish gray colored, loosely cemented, thin bedded to massive, fine to medium-grained and slightly micaceous siltstone. This formation contains numerous Pelecypods, gastropod shells and other fossil fragments. The age of Kyaukkok Formation is Lower to Middle Miocene (Fig.4).

Figure (4) Fossiliferous siltstone outcrop of the Kyaukkok Formation (Facing 130°) (N 17°21'45", E 96°13'50")

Obogon Formation

The Obogon Formation is the youngest stratigraphic unit of the Upper Pegu Group. It is well exposed on the Yangon-Mandalay Highway and Hledon Chaung. The Obogon Formation is mainly composed of sand and shale alternations. Sand layers are medium to thick bedded, coarse-grained, loosely cemented, reddish coloured on the weathered surface. Shale layers are thin-medium bedded, fine-grained, yellowish to buff coloured. They contain clay or mud pebbles. In this rock units, sedimentary structures such as small scale cross lamination, trough cross lamination, medium scale planar cross lamination are observed in Figure (5). Toward the upper part, their thickness gradually decreases and beds become more parallel. The age of the Obogon Formtion is middle Miocene.

Figure (5) Thin-laminated shale with intercalated sandstone of the Obogon Formation (Facing 280°) (N 17°21'38", E 96°14'00")

Irrawaddy Formation

It is widely distributed in the investigated area. This formation is mainly made up of yellowish to reddish coloured, medium to coarse grained, loosely cemented sandstones. It contains quartz pebbles. Iron rich hard bands are intercalated as interlayers. This formation unconformably rests upon the Obogon Formation of Upper Pegu Group, but there is no evidence of distinct unconformable contact. The age of this formation is Upper Miocene to Pliocene. (Fig.6)

Figure (6) Quartz pebbles in loosely cemented sandstones of the Irrawaddy Formation (Facing 130°) (N 17°20'32", E 96°13'35")

Laterite and lateritic soils

Laterite and lateritic soils are widely distributed in the study area as older alluvium unit. Complete lateritization processes took place at the foot of the Myoyootaung range. They are divided into A, B and C layers. "A" layer consists of topsoil with humus. "B" layer is subdivided into layer by layer. The uppermost part of the B layer is yellowish to reddish colored soil, and then reddish coloured lateritic soil with iron nodules and aluminium oxides and few quartz layers. Light grey or ashy coloured clay layer is underlain by iron nodule layer. Then, yellowish coloured, friable loose sand layers are present. Peat layer is intercalated within the friable loose sand layer. 'C' layer is lowermost laterite layer. The reddish coloured lateritic clay with concentration of iron and aluminium oxides is exposed along the Myoyootaung range. Indurated laterites are cropped out in the northeast part of Mignon village (N 17°20'12", E 96°12'55"). In the study area, lateritization may be shifted from the Irrawaddy Formation (Fig. 7&8).

Figure (7) Laterite succession found at the base of the Shweyaungdaw Pagoda (Facing 260°) (N 17°20'12", E 96°12'55")

Figure (8) Lateritic clay with iron and aluminium oxides (Facing 260°) (N 17°20'12", E 96°12'55")

Alluvium

The most widespread unit of the study area is alluvial soil. Predominant types of sediments are sand, silt and clay. Older alluvium consisting of lateritic clay, laterite and hill gravels (2 mm-3 cm in diameter) is observed as caps of the hills. Gravel bands are found on the lateritic clay at the Myoyootaung range. They are rounded to sub-rounded pebbles. Thin veneer of recent sediments is also found on the outcrops (Fig. 9).

Figure (9) Gravel band of the younger alluvium

Figure (10) Geology and soil sample localities map of Mingon Area

Stratigraphy of Meyon area

In Meyon area, metasedimentary rocks of Mergui Group and igneous rocks are exposed. The rocks consist of slate, argillite, phyllite and quartzite whose mineral assemblages of chlorite, andalusite and quartz indicate green schist facies. Granite intrusion exposed in the northern part of the Atat Ingabo village extends to the Taunggu-Mawchi granite belt. They are deformed by regional metamorphism and later hydrothermal alteration. The rare occurrence of volcanic rocks is rhyolite and rhyolitic tuff (Chhibber, 1934). The rock sequences of the study area are shown in Table 2.

Table (2) Rock sequences of Meyon Area

Succession	Age	Stratigraphic Symbol
Younger Alluvium	Holocene	Q _{2al}
Older Alluvium (Laterite and lateritic soil)	Pleistocene	Q _{1al}
Metasedimentary Rocks		
Mergui Group Slate, phyllite, schist and quartzite	Carboniferous?	C _{mg}
Igneous Rocks		
Breccias	Cenozoic ?	Cz _γ
Cream to pinkish, medium grained rhyolite	Mesozoic	Mz _α
Coarse grained biotite granite		Mz _τ

Igneous Rocks

Granite

Granite is mainly exposed in the northern part of the study area. It is coarse-grained, massive and equigranular. Quartzofeldspathic veins intruded the granite.

Rhyolite is cropped out in the Gugu and Kyaukpon prospect area. It is light pink to cream in color, strongly silicified and is cut by quartz veinlets.

Metasedimentary Rocks

The metasedimentary rocks of the Mergui Group are only exposed east of Kyaukpon prospect area. They are the oldest rock units in this area. They are slate, phyllite and schist. These are interbedded with minor quartzite.

The slate possesses reddish brown colour and perfect fissility. It is well exposed near the Kyaukpon prospect area (Fig.11).

Phyllite is black to brownish in color, highly contorted and flexured. It is distributed near the Gugu prospect area and Kyaukgyi taung area. The outcrop nature of phyllite is greyish in colour and friable (Fig.12).

The schists are dark grey to grey in color, fine to medium grained. They crop out in the Kyaukpon prospect area. It is well exposed, highly contorted and interrupted by penetration of quartz veinlets. The rock unit contains feldspar, quartz and mica (Fig.13).

The fine-grained quartzite is found near the Kuaukpon prospect area. The grey, massive to poorly bedded quartzites are restricted to the Guku prospect area. It is predominantly composed of quartz clasts with a matrix of finer quartz and clays, and shows reddish coloration of iron oxide. (Fig.14)

Figure (11) The slate bed near the Kyaukpon Prospect (Facing 95°)

Figure(12) Greyish coloured, friable phyllite exposed east of the Gugu Prospect (Facing 120°) (N 17°24'55", E 96°59'55")

Figure (13) Highly jointed, friable schist exposed near the Kyaukpon Prospect (Facing 150°)

Figure (14) The outcrop nature of quartzite in the Kyaukpon Prospect (Facing 70°) (N 17°25'09", E 97°00')

Alluvium

Laterite and lateritic soils (Older alluvium)

Lateritic soils are widely distributed in the study area as older alluvium unit. Complete lateritization processes are not found in this area. Poorly exposed laterite is found at the junction of cart road and stream. Reddish colored lateritic soils are also exposed in the stream section (Fig.15).

Younger alluvium

The younger alluvial soil covers older units. Predominant types of sediments are sand and silt.

Figure (15) Poorly exposed lateritic outcrop in stream section Rhyolite (Facing 110°) (N 17°26'18", E 96°58'21")

Figure (16) Geology and soil sample localities map of the Meyon Area

Geochemical Analysis of the Research Areas

The chemical results from Mington and Meyon areas analyzed by AAS are shown in Appendices. According to the chemical analyses, lateritic soil of Mington area contains Mn, Fe, Na, K, Ca and Mg elements. Manganese value range is from 125 ppm to 320 ppm. The mean value of manganese is 188.21 ppm and its standard deviation is 29.052 ppm. The maximum value of iron is 7150 ppm and the minimum value is 9890 ppm. The mean value of iron is 8357.04 ppm and its standard deviation is 720.856 ppm. Calcium value of range is from 160 ppm and 870 ppm. The mean value of calcium in the study area is 221.73 ppm and its standard deviation is 85.874 ppm. The minimum value of magnesium is 135 ppm and the maximum value is 195 ppm. The mean value is 163.17 ppm. The standard deviation is 15.023 ppm. The sodium concentration range is from 150 ppm to 250 ppm. The mean value of sodium is 184.96 ppm and its standard deviation is 21.718 ppm. The minimum content of potassium is 210 ppm and the maximum content is 430 ppm in soil sample. The mean value of potassium was observed as 367.06 ppm and its standard deviation is 38.234 ppm. Most of the elements are lithophile elements. These elements are mainly distributed on the earth crust.

Lateritic soil of Meyon area contains Au, Ag, Cu, Pb, Zn, Mn, Fe, Na, K, Ca, Mg elements. The minimum value of silver is 0.012 ppm and the maximum value is 1.584 ppm. The mean value is 0.24 ppm and its standard deviation is 0.309 ppm. Copper value range is from 30 ppm to 85 ppm. The mean value is 44.93 ppm. The standard deviation is 13.80 ppm. The minimum value of zinc is 35 ppm and the maximum value is 105 ppm. The mean value of zinc is 78.89 ppm and its standard deviation is 26.409 ppm. Manganese value range is from 55 ppm and the maximum value is 95 ppm. The mean value is 66.44 ppm and its standard deviation is 8.992 ppm. The iron concentration in soil samples are from 7340 ppm to 9980 ppm. The mean value of iron 8986.48 ppm and its standard deviation is 6632.841 ppm. Lead value range is from 20 ppm to 210 ppm. The mean value is 44.93 ppm and its standard deviation is 13.80 ppm. The minimum content of sodium is 75 ppm and the maximum content is 189 ppm in soil samples. Sodium was observed as 118.57 ppm and its standard deviation is 27.0 ppm. The potassium concentration in soil samples is from 65 ppm to 105 ppm. The mean value of potassium is 81.11 ppm and its standard deviation is 5.885 ppm. The minimum content of calcium is 58 ppm and the maximum content is 85 ppm in soil samples. The mean value was observed as 66.33 ppm and its standard deviation is 4.972 ppm. Magnesium value range is from 75 ppm to 92 ppm. The mean value of magnesium is 82.67 ppm and its standard deviation is 4.112 ppm. In this area lithophile elements are associated with siderophile and chalcophile elements. Siderophile and chalcophile elements are mainly concentrated in the core.

Figure (17) Distribution of Mn for the Mington area

Figure (18) Distribution of Fe for the Mington area

Figure (19) Distribution of Ca for the Mington area

Figure (20) Distribution of Mg for the Mington area

Figure (21) Distribution of Na for the Mington area

Figure (22) Distribution of K for the Mington area

Figure (23) Distribution of Ag for the Meyon area

Figure (24) Distribution of Cu for the Meyon area

Figure (27) Distribution of Fe for the Meyon area

Figure (28) Distribution of Pb for the Meyon area

Figure (29) Distribution of Na for the Meyon area

Figure (30) Distribution of K for the Meyon area

Figure (31) Distribution of Ca for the Meyon area

Cluster analysis of elements in soil in Mingon area

Proximity matrix in lateritic soil of Mingon area as shown in Table.3. Dendrogram of elements in the study area was completed to determine the element associations or cluster analysis based on proximity matrix of lateritic soils.

Cluster analysis of trace element associations was constructed by using single linkage. The lateritic soil sample of the study area presented is in the three different association groups. The first group consists of Mn, Na and Ca. It is the strongest association group. The second group composed of Fe and K. The third group of Mg was related to the former group. All of the groups represent the lithophile association in soil. They are most concentrated in the Earth’s crust.

Table (3) Proximity Matrix of the Mingon Area

Case	Matrix File Input					
	Mn	Fe	Na	K	Ca	Mg
Mn	.000	167.725	105.623	161.262	110.917	168.134
Fe	167.725	.000	187.473	137.869	160.545	186.836
Na	105.623	187.473	.000	149.089	179.887	192.123
K	161.262	137.869	149.089	.000	191.614	184.293
Ca	110.917	160.545	179.887	191.614	.000	164.574
Mg	168.134	186.836	192.123	184.293	164.574	.000

Single Linkage

Agglomeration Schedule

Stage	Cluster Combined		Coefficients
	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	
1	1	3	105.623
2	1	5	110.917
3	2	4	137.869
4	1	2	149.089
5	1	6	164.574

Dendrogram

Hierachical cluster analysis

Cluster analysis of elements in soil in Meyon area

Proximity matrix of the lateritic soil in Meyon area is as shown in Table.4. Dendrogram of elements in the study area was completed to determine the element associations or cluster analysis based on proximity matrix of the lateritic soils.

Cluster analysis of trace element associations was constructed by using single linkage. The lateritic soil sample of the study area presented the four different associations groups. The first group consists of Cu, Na and K. It is the strongest association group. The second group composed of Fe and Ca. They represent the lithophile (Na, K and Ca) groups element association. The third group consists of Pb, Mn and Zn. It represents the chalcophile (Pb,Zn) group elements association. Finally, the fourth group of Mg is related to the former three groups.

Table (4) Proximity Matrix of Meyon Area

Case	Matrix File Input								
	Cu	Pb	Zn	Mn	Fe	Na	K	Ca	Mg
Cu	.000	35.730	83.984	77.263	91.618	35.301	67.986	101.819	116.553
Pb	35.730	.000	68.044	43.727	122.492	85.183	100.226	106.136	138.298
Zn	83.984	68.044	.000	76.196	120.554	106.100	119.028	84.643	115.099
Mn	77.263	43.727	76.196	.000	120.482	95.108	77.564	89.894	119.794
Fe	91.618	122.492	120.554	120.482	.000	58.343	85.167	68.016	90.707
Na	35.301	85.183	106.100	95.108	58.343	.000	54.081	66.805	101.796
K	67.986	100.226	119.028	77.564	85.167	54.081	.000	80.501	118.316
Ca	101.819	106.136	84.643	89.894	68.016	66.805	80.501	.000	91.030
Mg	116.553	138.298	115.099	119.794	90.707	101.796	118.316	91.030	.000

Average Linkage (Between Groups)

Agglomeration Schedule

Stage	Cluster Combined		Coefficients	Stage Cluster First Appears		Next Stage
	Cluster 1	Cluster 2		Cluster 1	Cluster 2	
1	1	6	35.301	0	0	3
2	2	4	43.727	0	0	5
3	1	7	61.034	1	0	6
4	5	8	68.016	0	0	6
5	2	3	72.120	2	0	7
6	1	5	80.709	3	4	7
7	1	2	94.959	6	5	8

Agglomeration Schedule

Dendrogram

***** HIERARCHICAL CLUSTER ANALYSIS *****

Dendrogram using single Linkage

Uses of laterite and lateritic soil

Lateritic soils are widely used as fill materials for various construction works in most tropical countries. These soils are used as a road making material and they form the sub-grade of most tropical road. They are used as sub base and bases for low cost roads and these carry low to medium traffic. Furthermore, they are used as building material for molding of blocks and plastering. Their scopes are very wide and include civil engineering, agronomic, mining research (iron, aluminum and manganese) deposits. Lateritic soils are interesting because the natural relative abundance of these soils, availability, favorable engineering properties have been very useful for construction of foundation, roads, airfields, low-cost housing and compacted fill in earth embankments. Laterites have been applied to trace arsenic concentration from contaminated water. Lateritic soils are well suited for rubber tree plantations, fruit growing and horticulture. The studied areas are used as lateritic soil for road making materials and cultivation especially cashew, rubber and oil-palm.

Discussion and Conclusion

In this research, two lateritic soil areas have been investigated. The laterite and lateritic soil were secondary materials altered from the underlying bedrock. Mingon area is formed of Kyaukkok Formation, Obogon Formation, and Irrawaddy Formation. They were covered by alluvial sediments. Laterite and lateritic soil of Mingon area was altered from the underlying Irrawaddy Formation. In Meyon area, igneous rocks and metasedimentary rocks are cropped out. They covered by the older alluvium; laterite and lateritic soil and younger alluvium. The laterite and lateritic soils of Meyon area was altered from underlying igneous and metasedimentary rocks.

Lateritic soil of Mingon area contains Mn, Fe, Na, K, Ca and Mg elements. In this area, Mn, Mg, Na are shown symmetrical distribution. So, they are equally distributed in the study area. Fe and Ca show positive skewness and K is negative skewness. The lateritic soil samples are presented in the three different associations groups. The first group consists of Mn, Na and

Ca. It is the strongest association group. The second group composed of Fe and K. The third group of Mg was related to the former group.

Lateritic soil of Meyon area contains Ag, Au, Cu, Pb, Zn, Mn, Fe, Na, K, Ca and Mg. In this area, distributions of Cu, Zn, Mn, Pb, K, Ca, Na are shown symmetrical. So, they are equally distributed in the study area. Silver shows positive skewness and it is associated with gold. So, silver is distributed in the eastern part of the area because it is a gold prospect area. Fe shows negative skewness and it is distributed in the western part of the area because lateritic soil is more exposed than eastern part. The lateritic soil samples are presented the four different associations groups. The first group consists of Cu, Na and K. It is the strongest association group. The second group composed of Fe and Ca. They represent the lithophile (Na, K and Ca) groups element association. The third group consists of Pb, Mn and Zn. It represents the chalcophile (Pb,Zn) group elements association. Finally, the fourth group of Mg is related to the former three groups.

Lateritic soils are widely used as fill materials for various construction works in most tropical countries. These soils are used as a road making material and they form the sub-grade of most tropical road. They are used as sub base and bases for low cost roads and these carry low to medium traffic. Furthermore, they are used as building material for molding of blocks and plastering. Their scopes are very wide and include civil engineering, agronomic, mining research (iron, aluminum and manganese) deposits. These soils are poor engineering properties such as high plasticity, poor workability, low strength, high permeability, tendency to retain moisture and high natural moisture content. The effective use of these soils is often hindered by difficulty. So lateritic soil can only be utilized after modification/stabilization. Previously, the most commonly used additive for soil modification or stabilization is the ordinary Portland cement. In recent years that can be treatment by the addition of fly ash. The simplest stabilization process consists of taking soil and drying it in open-air. Mineralization is possible in lateritization areas. But every mineralization is not associated with lateritization. In Meyon area, primary and secondary gold mineralizations are found. Lateritic soils are well suited for rubber tree plantations, fruit growing and horticulture. In the study areas lateritic soils are used as a road making material and cultivation such as cashew, rubber and oil-palm.

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Appendix 1

Table 3 Trace element content in soil samples of Mingon Area (Unit - ppm)

Sr. No	Sample No.	Mn	Fe	Na	K	Ca	Mg
1	A-1	155	8320	165	365	210	190
2	A 0	190	8460	160	360	220	195
3	A 1	190	9150	185	390	195	180
4	A 2	195	8780	175	385	190	185
5	Out 1 B – 1	160	9170	180	385	220	185
6	B 0	155	8100	165	395	195	185
7	B 1	190	7980	165	385	210	190
8	B 2	185	7950	170	390	215	195
9	Out 1 C 0	175	8430	155	350	160	160
10	C 1	170	7170	210	380	165	155
11	C 2	170	8360	185	340	170	150
12	Out 1 D 0	175	8320	192	390	190	170
13	D 1	160	8450	185	410	195	175
14	D 2	165	8320	165	425	180	185
15	Out 1 E – 1	195	8560	180	395	185	140
16	E 0	190	8250	180	390	195	165
17	E 1	195	8150	185	385	180	155
18	E 2	190	8350	165	395	185	158
19	Out 1 F – 1	185	8170	195	360	185	175
20	F 0	190	7850	180	370	175	160
21	F 1	195	7990	190	370	170	165
22	F 2	195	7640	180	385	165	165
23	Out 1 G 0	168	8450	180	425	175	150
24	G 1	170	8300	185	410	190	165
25	G 2	165	8250	170	430	195	180
26	Out 1 H 0	190	8200	220	360	195	185
27	H 1	195	8350	215	350	195	185